

**22NRM03 “Metrology to support standardisation of hydrogen fuel sampling
for heavy duty hydrogen transport”**

Report A1.1.2

**Review of the current sampling systems that are used for the quality control sampling of hydrogen
at HD-HRS**

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Summary

This review was written as part of activity A1.1.2 from the Partnership on Metrology project “Metrology to support standardisation of hydrogen fuel sampling for heavy duty hydrogen transport” (MetHyTrucks). The three-year European project started 1st June 2023.

This report will review the current sampling systems that are used for the quality control sampling of hydrogen at HD-HRS. For each reviewed system, the report will include a detailed list of their limitations, especially in terms of the sample volume, pressure, maximum flow, station status and configuration. The review will also investigate and report on hydrogen gas and particulate sampling. For the systems that are currently used at light duty hydrogen refuelling stations, the report will include a discussion on the steps needed to adapt the systems to HD applications.

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1 Introduction

Hydrogen is an energy carrier that has been studied in the last two decades to create a more carbon-neutral future. Energy that is generated from sources such as sunlight, water flow, wind or biomass can be stored as hydrogen (from water electrolysis, biomass gasification) and be used at a later moment. Hydrogen can be used to generate electricity through a fuel cell system and then power an electrical engine. Due to the low mass of hydrogen, its energy density and its ability to be compressed, a large volume of hydrogen can be contained in a reservoir, allowing a heavy-duty vehicle to drive over long distances (i.e., 1000 km on one tank) [1]. The second advantage of hydrogen is that the tank can be rapidly refilled, similar to petrol tanks. A tank can be fully refilled in approximately 15 minutes. Therefore, using hydrogen as an energy carrier is particularly interesting for the transportation sector [2]. Hydrogen at hydrogen refuelling stations (HRS) is compressed to 35-70 MPa and is used to refuel vehicles via a dispenser [3]. Recently, a new version of the Alternative Fuels Infrastructure Regulation (AFIR) was published. The AFIR states different national targets for hydrogen powered vehicles. One of the statements is that to ensure interoperability, publicly accessible hydrogen refuelling stations must at least deliver hydrogen at a pressure of 700 bar [4].

Figure 1 Schematic example of parallel filling of a sample cylinder for hydrogen quality analysis

The quality of the hydrogen fuel may have a direct effect on the fuel cell electrical vehicle performance, especially ultra-traces of sulphur may deteriorate performance or reduce the lifetime of the system. Heavy duty transportation is an extremely cost-efficient industry sector and vehicle lifetime is a cornerstone of the business model, therefore the impact of low-quality hydrogen fuel may be extremely detrimental to the transport business and hinder the deployment of this low carbon solution for heavy duty transport. International standards such as ISO 14687 [5] or EN17124 [6] define specific thresholds for a large range of chemical compounds in hydrogen fuel. To assure that the level of contaminants in hydrogen fuel dispensed at HRS is below the threshold specified in ISO 14687, sampling is performed before analysis. To be accurately executed, sampling should be done via validated sampling devices using standardized protocols. Currently, there is a lack of validated sampling devices for heavy duty (HD) HRS sampling and besides ASTM D7606 [7], standardized validation protocols do not exist.

Sampling at HRS is performed with the goal of collecting and analysing a sample that is representative of the hydrogen fuel that is received by a fuel cell electric vehicle (FCEV). Sampling systems should be simple and safe to operate and they should take representative samples to prevent the measurement of false positives or false negatives. This is of particular importance for H₂O and other reactive contaminants. Since there is no standardization or validation protocol in this field yet, companies have developed their own sampling system with corresponding internal protocols and procedures.

Nowadays a shift is happening from light duty (LD) to HD hydrogen use. Sampling from LD-HRS was studied in 19ENG04 MetroHyVe 2 [8], however most sampling systems were not designed for the expected flow in HD HRS (LD: flow up to 60 g/s and HD: flow up to 120g/s or 300 g/s). LD- and HD-HRS operate at different pressures and flows, therefore adaptations to the sampling devices should be made to accommodate for HD hydrogen refuelling. Furthermore, due to these adaptations, the safety aspects should be reassessed. The safety distance, compliance of the system and choice of components suitable for the HD conditions require serious evaluation to ensure a safe working environment.

This report describes an overview of existing sampling systems for LD and changes that need to be made to make them suitable for HD sampling. Note that on HD sampling systems, very little information is currently available in the open literature. Therefore, mainly information on LD sampling systems is provided. Lots of information on LD sampling can also be found in reports and articles from the MetroHyVe 2 project including a good practice guide on H₂ quality sampling [9] and a review article on sampling strategies [10]. Furthermore, ISO/DIS 19880-9 is currently under development and is expected to be published in 2024.

2 Current sampling systems

This review will contain information on seven different systems: the Linde Qualitizer, Hy-SaM, Air Liquide's H₂ sampling system, ENGIE's sampling device, NSP-7606 and NPL's two sampling systems. The information can be found in table 1. Further details such as limitations and future prospects of the systems will be discussed in this section.

The MetroHyVe2 report from activity A3.4.9 already concluded an analysis on the gaps between sampling at LD-HRS and HD-HRS [11]. One of the gaps is that sampling on LD-HRS and HD-HRS requires different nozzles and receptacles. For parallel sampling, it is a challenge to obtain nozzles for use at HD -40°C and 120g/s. Systems that use an orifice need to be adjusted to be able to control the flow, and pipework and fittings may need to be adjusted to the different flow and filling pressure. Systems that use a buffer tank instead of a vehicle will have to install a larger buffer tank at HD-HRS. For serial sampling, a receptacle is available that is compatible with both LD-HRS and HD-HRS. The HRS is in maintenance mode during sampling, so sample might be less representative for higher flow rates during filling.

A challenge that occurs at stations, is that sometimes the station operators are not prepared for taking a sample. For taking a sample, technical support is necessary. However, the technical support is not always present when needed.

2.1 Linde Qualitizer

The H₂ Qualitizer system has been developed by Linde. It is based on parallel sampling, and it has been described in detail in reference [10]. The Qualitizer allows a maximum pressure of 875 bar with a sealed safety valve being installed for to prevent exposure to higher pressures. The maximum reduced pressure is set to 160 bar [12]. The system is throttled with an orifice (0.33 mm) to the sample cylinder so that a sample is collected during the normal period for a refuelling of a passenger car FCEV. This means that even if the system receptacle is changed to accommodate for heavy duty application, the orifice still needs to be changed and calibrated for higher flow rates/different refuelling times. For the overall sampling device upstream, the orifice needs to be compliant with higher flow than 60 g/s. During MetroHyVe2, filling was performed at an average rate of 14.1 ± 1.0 g/s [9].

According to the manufacturer, purging of the instrument is not necessary before use. In the HyCoRa project, samples have been taken with the Linde Qualitizer. It was observed that with a pressure >100 bar, the sampling system will drain H₂ from the hose. Furthermore, the leak test will fail if the bottle valve is not closed. Besides, the system should not be used in heavy rain as ice can lock moving parts and prevent disassembly. Nonetheless, a major advantage of this system is that no safety override on all tested refuelling stations is needed.

2.2 Hy-SaM

The Hy-SaM sampling device, developed by ZBT and ZSW, is a 'gas parallel' system [10]. Sampling is performed without overriding the refuelling protocol. Venting to atmosphere without a FCEV is also possible.

Currently, the Hy-SaM apparatus only operates at 700 bar LD-HRS. A new Hy-SaM system is in development for HD-HRS with the following limitations:

- Sample volume: Sample cylinders of either 2.25 or 10L are preferred. However, in principle all sample volumes are possible. Up to three cylinders can be connected for consecutive or simultaneous sampling.
- Pressure:
 - Heavy duty pressure line: 350 bar
 - Light duty pressure line: 700 bar
 - Discrete line for sample of storage banks: up to 900 bar
 - Sample pressure: up to 90 bar
- Mass flow:
 - Light duty flow: 60 g/s
 - Heavy duty flow: 120 g/s

A limitation in the operation of the refuelling stations is that some stations do not allow automatic refuelling while taking a sample. During the pressure surge and leakage test, the station recognizes an additional volume and unexpected flow which causes an abort. Either the sampling should be stopped for a short period of time during the pressure surge, or refuelling should be done manually. However, it is challenging to get a representative sample when the pressure ramp does not follow a standardized protocol but is implemented manually.

To adapt the LD sampling system to HD, a 350 bar receptacle and nozzle will be installed and the piping sizes will be increased.

2.3 Air Liquide's H₂ sampling system

As described by Arrhenius et al. during the MetroHyVe 2 project [10], the Air Liquide's H₂ sampling system is a system operating the 'gas serial' method, in which the HRS nozzle is connected to the device receptacle. Sampling is performed through manual operation with hydrogen venting through a mobile vent. The device also contains a parallel line with a portable (moisture) analyser. Sampling cylinders should have a type E or DIN1 (DIN 477/1) fitting, otherwise intermediate fittings should be used. During MetroHyVe2, filling was performed at an average rate of 3.3 g/s [9].

No information is publicly available on the readiness for HD-HRS. As the system requires the HRS to be in maintenance mode, the flow and pressure of the HRS may be adjusted to the current design as it doesn't require high pressure or flow to collect the sample. The adaptation of the receptacle is the only engineering requirement for this system to be HD-HRS ready as long as the HRS parameters during the sampling are compliant with the Air Liquide's H₂ sampling system requirements.

2.4 ENGIE's sampling device

The sampling device developed by ENGIE operates via the 'gas serial' method and can only sample in two-ended valves [10]. For sampling with this device, opposed to other 'gas serial' sampling systems, it is not necessary to override the station's safety protocol. The biggest challenges for sampling with this sampling system are:

- Cleaning of sampling device
- Cleaning of the sampling cylinder before sampling
- Properly flushing the cylinders before closing

ENGIE has planned to adapt their system to HD-HRS. The modification has been done and the device can already operate at 350 bar and 120 g/s with a different receptacle, so no additional adaptations are needed. The volume of the tank is not implemented in the filling protocol at 350 bar, 120 g/s, so the station will not deliver H₂ without bypassing the fuelling protocol. To be able to sample without bypassing the safety protocol, the tank size (55 L) should be increased to 835 L (this also requires redesigning of the bench to accommodate such a large tank). New protocols are being developed with smaller tank volumes (around 420 L).

2.5 NSP-7606 (gaseous impurities) and MRM 7650 (particulates)

These systems have been developed by Airborne Labs International. Further, a sampling kit can be purchased which consists of 2 x 1 L Silconert passivated cylinders (with 2 valves) and 2x VHP particulate SS 47 mm filter assemblies. Whenever both gaseous impurities and particulates must be sampled, they recommend to first perform the particulate sampling (as the particles are typically not distributed homogeneously throughout the H₂ gas phase as volatile gaseous impurities & contaminants will be). For the gaseous impurities, cylinders are first purged and then filled to 68 bar, and a replicate is made. The MRM 7650 sampling system can be used for flow rates up to 125 g/s [13].

2.6 NPL HD direct sampling (gaseous impurities)

The NPL HD direct sampling device is a system operating the 'gas serial' method, in which the HRS nozzle is connected to the device receptacle. Sampling is performed through manual operation with venting hydrogen through a mobile vent. The device also allows sampling with single ended or double ended cylinders and allows flowthrough of the sampling cylinder to allow additional purging. Sampling cylinders should have a DIN 477 n.1 fitting. The sampling cylinder fill can be throttled by a needle valve to adjust a filling rate from 1.4 to 11.5 g/s.

2.7 NPL HD parallel sampling (gaseous impurities)

The 1.1 NPL HD parallel sampling (gaseous impurities) device, as seen in Figure 1, realises the sampling without overriding the refuelling protocol. Venting to atmosphere without a FCEV is also possible through the portable vent of the sampling system.

Figure 2. Schematic of NPL HD parallel sampling system

This new sampling system can realise LD-HRS sampling at 70 MPa and HD-HRS sampling at 35 MPa. The system requires sampling cylinders of 10 L with a DIN 477 N.1 valve. However, other cylinder volumes are also possible as long as the throttling valve is adjusted accordingly. This new sampling system is under commissioning and will require validation to ensure it provides reliable results.

A limitation in the operation of the refuelling stations is that some stations do not allow automatic refuelling while taking a sample. During the pressure surge and leakage test, the station recognizes an additional volume and unexpected flow which causes an abort. Either the sampling should be stopped for a short period of time during the pressure surge, or refuelling should be done manually. The system is not communicating which may be a problem for some station software and novel safety requirements. The sampling system can be upgraded to communication.

3 Summary

Many different sampling systems are in operation but currently typically only for LD vehicles. Some new systems are currently being developed or are in the testing phase like the NPL parallel sampling system. Some of the existing LD sampling systems, like the Hy-SAM and ENGIE's system are currently being adapted for sampling at HD-HRS. At this stage, the required engineering adaptations seem to be relatively minor like use of another receptacle and use of larger piping to adapt to the higher flow rates. However, safety distance, compliance of the system and choice of components suitable for the HD conditions require serious evaluation to ensure safety and representative samples will be achieved. These aspects will be investigated in Work Package 1, 2 and 3 of the MetHyTrucks project.

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Table 1. Sampling systems to use at hydrogen refuelling stations. Information retrieved from Arrhenius et al [4] and manufacturers.

System	Manufacturer	Type (serial/parallel/direct)	Pressure	Sampling duration	Average filling rate during MetroHyVe	Sample Volume	Cylinder	Override safety system HRS	Potential for adaptation to HD?	Remarks
Qualitizer	Linde	Parallel	35 MPa and 70 MPa	<3 min	14.1 ± 1.0 g/s	Typically 10 L. Filled to 90-130 bar.	Linde uses one-ended aluminum cylinders with no specific treatment and SINTEF uses SPECTRA-SEAL® cylinders with stainless steel valve.	No		Principally a T-piece where a sample is collected while an FCEV is refueled.
Hy-SaM	ZSW and ZBT	Parallel	70 MPa	2-5 min	15.3 ± 2.2 g/s	2.25 or 10 L. Filled to 80-90 bar.	One-ended aluminum SPECTRA-SEAL® cylinder with stainless steel valve or stainless-steel cylinders internally coated with Sulfinert®	No	Yes, this is planned	Completely passivated system
H2 Sampling System	Air Liquide	Serial	Compatible with 88 MPa for passenger vehicles and 35 MPa for heavy duty	<1 min/cylinder	3.3 g/s	5L. Filled to 150 bar.	Aluminum cylinder (no specific treatment) with double-ended stainless-steel valves	Manual mode operation		
	ENGIE	Serial	35 MPa and 70 MPa	<3 min	3.9 ± 0.6 g/s	1 L, but 0.5 to 5 L cylinders can be used. Filled to 80-90 bar.	Stainless steel double-ended valve cylinder coated with Sulfinert®	No	Yes, this is planned	Can also be used for online analysis of water and oxygen. Uses 55-L tank to simulate the presence of a FCEV vehicle.
NSP-7606 (compliant with ASTM D7606-17 (HQSA))	Airborne laboratories International	Serial	35 MPa and 70 MPa	<1 min/cylinder		1 L, but 0.5 to 2 L cylinders can be used. Filled to 68 bar.	Stainless steel double-ended valve cylinder internally coated with silicon	Manual mode operation		Airborne has a large online analytical system (HyEx-2719) in development.
NPL HD direct sampling	NPL	Serial			1.4 - 11.5 g/s		Single ended or double ended cylinders with a DIN 477 n.1 valve	Manual mode operation	Already adapted	Allows flowthrough of the sampling cylinder to allow additional purging
NPL HD parallel sampling	NPL	Parallel	35 MPa and 70 MPa			10L, but other volumes are possible	Cylinders with a DIN 477 n.1 valve	No	Already adapted	